

Dealing with doubts: Site georeferencing in archaeology and in the geosciences

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Abstract. This paper discusses three data-driven interdisciplinary use cases of dealing with and modelling vague and uncertain geo-references (findspots) based on literature as LOD from the archaeological and geosciences domain.

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1 Introduction

Archaeological research must handle doubts such as vagueness, uncertainty and ambiguities in data modelling. This occurs especially in georeferencing. However, creating reproducible and comprehensible data for re-use while guaranteeing data quality in archaeological data involves disclosing doubts and ambiguities [11]. This is also important for data FAIRification, addressed in the NFDI. Especially vagueness and uncertainty must be modelled to work with geodata. However, for linking data and FAIRification graph-based modelling as Linked Open Data (LOD) proposed by Berners-Lee (2006) [2] (cf. Schmidt et al. (2022) [10]) is the method and technique of choice. Due to the huge variety of research domains, an interdisciplinary, commonly understandable modelling of uncertainties and vagueness in research data is extremely challenging. We will present three data-driven interdisciplinary use cases of dealing with and modelling vague and uncertain geo-references (findspots) based on literature as LOD from the archaeological and geosciences domain.

2 Modelling Approaches

The main idea and goal is to publish and model the following information:

- describe where the geoinformation comes from
- describe the method of how the coordinate was created
- describe the uncertainty issue(s)
- use references into the Semantic Web

2.1 Wikidata

Figure 1: Ex-situ Ogham Stone with on-site survey. Florian Thierry CC BY 4.0.

Entities in Wikidata (here, an Ogham Stone) may have coordinates (P625). These coordinates contain uncertainty and reference information, which can be modelled using Wikidata qualifiers and references. In the case of Ogham Stones, which have been visited in on-site surveys, this can be done as follows (Figure 1):

- qualifier: P1180 sourcing circumstances
- qualifier: P248 stated in
- qualifier: P276 location
- qualifier: P459 determination method
- qualifier: P2868 subject has role
- reference: P11693 OpenStreetMap node ID

Figure 2: Ogham Stone: only Literature as Source. Florian Thierry CC BY 4.0.

Ogham Stones, which are only available in literature and/or online databases such as “Ogham in 3D” or CISP (Figure 2):

- qualifier: P248 stated in
- qualifier: P3831 object has role
- qualifier: P459 determination method
- qualifier: P2868 subject has role
- reference: P854 reference URL

2.2 Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology (FSLO)

The Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology is based on PROV-O, SKOS and GeoSPARQL. It follows the PROV-O concept of Entity, Activity and Agent (Figure 3). In the case of this ontology, Sites (entity) have a Geometry and were created using a Method (activity) by a Person (agent), c.f. Figure 4. The site and geometry include two properties to describe certainty: `fsl:certaintyDesc` and `fsl:certaintyLevel`; and sites on top properties to describe references to, e.g., books, `fsl:hasReference` and to online resources, e.g. via `exactMatch` properties from the SKOS vocabulary. The method can be described via sources (`fsl:hasSource`, `fsl:hasSourceType`), references (`fsl:hasReference`), method descriptions (`fsl:activityDesc`), and certainty information (`fsl:certaintyLevel`, `fsl:certaintyDesc`). The resulting Linked Open Data as RDF can be transformed into human-readable HTML files using the SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation research tool [5].

Figure 3: Schematic view of the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology based on the PROV-O ontology. Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0.

Figure 4: Schematic view of the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology and its relations, based on the PROV-O ontology. Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0.

2.3 Wikibase

The Wikibase modelling (Figure 5) is related to the Wikidata modelling approach. Here, a site also has a lat/lon coordinate, which has qualifier to describe it further:

- has certainty level
- certainty description
- method used
- acting person
- has source
- has source subtype
- method description

Figure 5: Wikibase Data Model of a site. Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0.

3 Use Cases

The aforementioned method can be applied to three use cases from the archaeological and geosciences domain: Ogham Stones in Ireland, Silver Coinage in Croton, and the Eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite.

3.1 Irish Ogham Stones (Wikidata)

Ogham stones are monoliths with the early medieval primitive Irish Ogham script, mostly erected on the island of Ireland and in the Western part of Britain between the 4th and 9th centuries. Most stones are no longer at the original site, which is important for cartographic recording and makes it more difficult to determine their original function [6]. Ogham stone sites are mentioned in several catalogues such as books, online databases, e.g., the CISP project or online repositories, e.g., Ogham in 3D. These sources give information in different granularities: townlands, descriptions, and coordinates in WGS84/GPS or Irish GRID references. This can be modelled, e.g., in Wikidata using CIIC 242, known as CISP PARAR/1, SMR No. KE066-016005- (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Ogham Stone CIIC 242 (SMR No. KE066-016005-) at the Aghadoe Church Ruin (SMR No. KE066-016001-) near 52,0767683, -9,5543233. Images by Florian Thiery, right-bottom: Map by © Open Street Map Contributors under Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation (OSMF), via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/10040757680> by fthierygeo. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.

This CIIC 242 Ogham Stone has the Wikidata Q identifier Q106680977. Geospatial information can be modelled for the on-site survey (in Open Street Map) and the Ogham in 3D database entry (Figure 7). The Open Street Map (OSM) node 10040757680 (<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/10040757680>) has the following information: source: survey by user @fthierygeo and the location 52,0767683, -9,5543233. This node is spatially related to the Aghadoe Church (way/378015315; Q30247109) in the Irish County Kerry. On top of that, the Ogham in 3D ID 242. _Parkavonear (https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/242._Parkavonear) stated: “GPS coordinates -9.554751, 52.076337.”

coordinate location

52°4'36.3659"N, 9°33'15.5639"W

sourcing circumstances	on-site survey
location	in situ
determination method	on-site survey
subject has role	archaeological site
stated in	OpenStreetMap

▼ 1 reference

OpenStreetMap node ID	10040757680
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+ add reference

52°4'34.813"N, 9°33'17.104"W

determination method	georeferencing
object has role	database entry (Ogham)
subject has role	archaeological site
stated in	dataset distribution

▼ 1 reference

reference URL	https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/242_Par_kavonear
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+ add reference

Figure 7: Coordinate locations (P625) of Ogham Stone CIIC 242 in Wikidata (Q106680977). Public Domain.

3.2 Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) ash airfall (LOD / FSLO)

The Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) ash airfall in Central Europe was derived from the Campania region in Italy and a late Pleistocene volcanic event [3, 1]. Around 40,000 yr b2k, the largest eruption of the CI took place in the Phlegraean Fields. Based on this, massive glass deposits from the CI-eruption covered large parts of the eastern European continent (Figure 8); volcanic material of the CI is often found in isolated watersheds and valleys. These findspots are recorded in several papers, e.g. precise coordinates, references to cities or references to regions.

One Findspot is Urluia in Romania. Spatial information about this findspot is mentioned in some papers, such as Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76 [4]: “[...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River.” or Pötter et al. (2021), p.5 [9]: “The Urluia [...] is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea [...]”. Investigations on OSM showed that this limestone quarry is described using way/84975654, resulting in a coordinate POINT(27.9021 44.0947). This can be modelled using the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology as Linked Open Data in `cisite_52` (https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cisite_52/index.html). Another example is a findspot at Crvena Stiljena Cave (Montenegro), mentioned in Morley and Woodward (2011) [8]. This findspot is also an archaeological site described in OSM node/10879170567 and several papers, such as Morin and Soulier (2017) [7], resulting in the LOD `cisite_51` (https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cisite_51/index.html).

Figure 8: Sample of Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots based on several literature. Florian Thiery and Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0.

3.3 Silver Coinage of Croton (Wikibase)

Research on the silver coinage of Croton, an Achaean colony in southern Italy from the 6th - 3rd century BC, e.g., examines the material under numismatic, historical, and archaeological methods to reconstruct the monetary history of the ancient city. The geo-locations of the finds are almost all not exactly georeferenced (e.g., by use of the documentation of excavation reports). The determined locations are derived from literature and have varying degrees of precision regarding the location of the find spot. An example of the uncertainty information of a find at Esaro River in 1967 shows the challenges:

“There is only the information that the hoard was found on the river Esaro, without specifying exactly where on the river course. In the literature, there is information that it was found "in Crotone", by which the city rather than the province is meant; otherwise, it would have been formulated differently. The urban area of the river course ends shortly after the "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". The most likely location for the find is along the course of the river between the section just before the motorway and the mouth of the river in the sea. Since the find was made in 1967, the river's course at that time probably corresponds fairly closely to the course of the river today. However, both the latter and the presumed find section are conjectures.”

This information is modelled using the Wikibase approach as entity Q67 and can be shown in a wikibase.cloud instance for fuzzy-sl at <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q67>.

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